

Local Integration of the South Sudanese Refugee: Exploring Impact on the Neighboring States

Sumaya Khan Auntu, Faria Nusrat & Sumaiya Siddika

Abstract:

After an internationally recognized referendum on self-determination, South Sudan became independent on 9 July 2011 by the end of Africa's one of the longest civil wars. Afterwards, South Sudan entered its civil war on December 15, 2013. It happened between the two governing bodies of South Sudan President Salva Kiir and Vice President Riek Machar. The African Union, the United Nations, the United States, and the other Western forces had made major diplomatic attempts to bring the war to an end but failed. In response to this civil war, mass people of South Sudan have started to take refuge in the neighbouring states. More than 1.6 million people have been internally displaced, with approximately 200,000 finding shelter at UN PoC sites in front of UN bases. They fall under troublesome situations in the receiving countries as well. Though the United States along with other international organizations have significant political, financial, and military investments in the refugee receiving countries by the war in South Sudan, such as Ethiopia, Uganda, and Kenya, local integration is not still welcomed by them. Though this paper has some limitation like its only qualitative based research so there is lack of resources for explaining overall situation. In spite of some limitation the study will try to evaluate the impacts of the South Sudanese Refugee Crisis on the neighbouring states through local integration with the secondary data collected from different books, journals, newspapers, articles, etc. By following the qualitative research approach. Basically this paper has two purpose. Firstly it explains the historical background of conflict. Secondly it describes the impact on neighbouring states in various event of life. In conclusion, finally, some policies will be recommended which have present implication to solve the conflict and ensure the proper treatment of refugee who take shelter in different neighbouring states.

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Literature review

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1. Introduction

Previously at the ending point of the 19th century, Sudan was under British Egyptian ruling power. At that time, the northern part of Sudan could adopt the British culture, knowledge, and technique as a result, they moved towards development (Knopf, 2016). On the other hand, the Southern part had rejected them. Finally, in 1956, Sudan has got its independence. But right at that moment, another problem had been started. South and North were possessing different religions, cultures, and ethnic values. By which they could not stay together (Peterson and Hovil, 2004). Moreover, the northern Sudanese people were trying to impose the Shariah law over the mass Sudanese people that initiate a long-term civil war in Sudan. In 2005, after signing the Comprehensive Peace Treaty, a new nation was born named South Sudan (Knopf, 2016). The election has been taken place. One electoral government has posted it in 2011. President Salva Kiir and Vice President Riek Macher were involved in personal political issues (Peterson and Hovil, 2004). In late 2012, President Salva Kiir accused his vice president Riek Macher of this planned coup and sacked his entire cabinet (Knopf, 2016). It has given birth to another conflict in South Sudan. Salva Kiir and Riek Macher are from two tribal groups hence this issue had created ethnic conflict as well (Peterson and Hovil, 2004). The conflict has snatched innumerable lives and forced millions of people. Displaced from their homes whom all are even deprived of their basic needs (Knopf, 2016). Two million people have been turned into refugees who all have taken shelter in the neighbor states and another two million internally displaced and have taken shelter in different neighboring countries. It is considered the biggest refugee crisis in Africa (Kline, 2003). These receiving countries are already struggling with their own crises. For example, the ongoing conflict in Somalia, the escalating war in Yemen, the increased volatility in Kenya prior to the 2017 presidential elections, the internal conflicts in Sudan and the deadly political protest as well as devastating drought in Ethiopia. On the other hand, Intra-regional tensions like rivalry between Sudan and Uganda, competition for regional hegemony between Uganda and Ethiopia, both have worsen the conflicts in South Sudan (Knopf, 2016).

The purpose of the study is to discover the impacts of the South Sudanese Refugee Crisis on the neighboring states through local integration. Therefore, the following question I have followed in this research paper- How does the south Sudanese refugee crisis spread its impact on the neighboring states through local integration?

2. Methodology

A qualitative research design has been used in this study. There were secondary data collected from different books, journals, newspaper, articles, etc. Data has been distributed in a descriptive order. It was verified with various sources and later organized into several headings.

3. Theoretical Framework

The policymakers of south Sudan follow the footsteps supported by the ideology of classical realism. President Salva Kiir and Vice President Riek Machar are involved in political and ethnic conflict due to belonging to different tribal zone and differences of opinion in quest of power (Vasquez, 1998). Individual power interest (classical realism) of each of them is motivated to engage in a long-term civil war inside the country that have compelled a huge number of civilians to take refugee (Vasquez, 1998). This South Sudanese refugee crisis can be described push and pull theory of migration as well.

South Sudanese civilians are leaving their country due to insecurity, political instability, drought, and famine (Kline, 2003). The present conditions of south Sudan are creating a huge playground of unemployment. These all are acting as push factors for South Sudanese to take refuge in the neighboring states (Kline, 2003). On the other hand, they are taking refuge in the host country with the hope of availability of better job opportunities, better standard of livelihood, religious freedom, political freedom as well as environmental safety. These all are acting as pull factors for South Sudanese refugees to take refuge in the neighboring states (Kline, 2003).

4. Literature Review

Tonleu (2018) stated that the South Sudanese refugee crisis is the result of conflict between two governing bodies of South Sudan (Kaiser, 2010). There are 2.5 million refugees of South Sudan. Most of them are women and children who all have witnessed the destruction of their families in front of their eyes (Kaiser, 2010). These refugees are mainly fleeing to all six neighboring states.

- i. Uganda (45%)
- ii. Sudan (30%)
- iii. Ethiopia (18%)
- iv. Kenya (5%)
- v. Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) (4%)
- vi. Central African Republic (1%) (Kaiser, 2010).

The international committee of Red Cross(2014) stated in their report that the long term conflict has already caused 1.5 million death, 2 million internal displacement, and 2 million refugee in the neighboring states due to food insecurity, famine, drought, an outbreak of different diseases like Cholera, Diarrhoea, etc. (Blanchard,2014). Along with some humanitarian crises like war crimes, genocide, rape, etc. Several peace treaties had been signed by the two parties whom all are initiating the resolve the conflict but fail (Blanchard, 2014)

South Sudan Refugee Response Plan (2019-20) enlighten with the hope of increased funding for 2019-20 of the interest of the host country for resettlement that will significantly reduce the pressure over the recent host countries so that they can concentrate on ensuring the better living conditions for the refugee and enhance their resilience (Hansen,2018). Resources and government initiatives are required to initiate local integration along with immediate measures taken by the legal guardian of international refugees, UNHCR, and different international organizations to resolute the conflict-prone situation so that voluntary repatriation can be encouraged (Blanchard, 2014). Addressing the current south Sudanese governing bodies' sufficient amount of documentation should be presented to the rest of the world. The increasing rate of South Sudanese refugees is increasing at an alarming rate in the neighboring above mentioned five states that are facing problems to manage them. For example, the Comprehensive Refugee Response Framework had been adopted in Ethiopia, Uganda, and Kenya but still not up to the mark. Sudan and DRC should get support from outside of the camp area. The present condition of South Sudan cannot be encouraged for voluntary repatriation since their return is neither safe nor sustainable. Civilians of South Sudan are still afraid of physical or sexual violence like war crimes, rape, and robbery. In one interview telecast on the Amnesty International of one 9 years old child taking refuge from South Sudan. He explained that he felt afraid to return back to his

country of origin since he had witnessed the death of his father and the rape of his mother. They consider voluntary repatriation as a football game as they know the problems of their residing area and their insecurity after their repatriation (Hovil et al., 2015). The South Sudanese refugee are not receiving the standard living conditions in the host country. For example, DRC and South Sudan are deliberately failing to offer them adequate access to the labor market and reduce poverty. Uganda is struggling to provide them proper education and skill development training so that they are failing to contribute to their national economy. Kenya and Ethiopia are failing to provide the proper health care and hygiene that result in the outbreak of different diseases (Hovil et al., 2015).

In recent time refugee crisis is worldwide headache. The article name “challenges and Boons of Refugee on the Host Communities: In the Case of Benishangul-Gumuz Regional state, Western Ethiopia” by Tadele Tesfaye Labiso pointed that Ethiopia is the second largest host country who always take huge number of refugee. Those refugee possessed security threat of the host country of Ethiopia. South Sudan conflict created the burden over host country (Labiso, 2020). Recent pandemic hit everyone. The recent article name “Protecting South Sudanese Refugees from COVID-19” by Iman Mustafa and Khamis Mohamed explained that Sudan hosts over 800,000 South Sudanese refugees. Because of recent pandemic situation many international organization like UNICEF is trying to solve health related problem. They are not only working refugee but also host countries because they are already burdened by refugee influx besides recent Pandemic create another discomfort situation to look after the huge refugees. (Mustafa and Mohamed, 2020)

5. Impacts of local integration on the neighboring states

These neighboring countries are facing several problems of their own, hereby, these increased numbers of the refugees have become an extra burden on them (Auntu et al., 2021). The impacts of local integration on the neighboring states due to South Sudanese Refugee Crisis are represented below.

5.1 Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC)

Some 95,181 South Sudanese refugees are residing in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC). They are mainly residing in the camp area and their local integration procedures had been adopted in the Haut Uele and Uri provinces which are open-door asylum (Saksena and McMorrow, 2019). But the socio-economic conditions of the Democratic Republic of Congo are poor. As a result, both DRC civilians and South Sudanese refugees need to rely on RRP for humanitarian assistance and to cope up with this problem DRC government has opened a market economy so that refugee can take over their responsibility without any foreign aid (Saksena and McMorrow, 2019). Still, there are security threats in the border area along with a poor standard of livelihood. Started from free access to the market economy to resettlement, DRC is facing a poor situation in lack of proper medical services, efficient staffs, medicines (Auntu et al., 2021). Half of the South Sudanese refugees have less access to primary health care in the Democratic Republic of Congo. Moreover, 40% of them are school-going children (Saksena and McMorrow, 2019). Previously, there are problems in admitting them into school but now RRP provides them educational facilities. At present, water and sanitation procedures have become a matter of concern as 11.4 liters of water are allotted per

person/day and only 23% of them were facilitating with drop hole latrine (Saksena and McMorrow, 2019).

5.2 Ethiopia

Almost 422, 240 refugees from South Sudan are taking shelter in Ethiopia (Meyer et al., 2019). From the beginning, Ethiopia is working as a host country for the refugee. Compared with the other countries refugee are in a better position here. Still, due to poor vaccination coverage Cholera had outbroken in South Sudan. Among the South Sudanese refugees, about 91% are living in refugee camps in the Gambelia region in Ethiopia (Martin, 2016). The government is trying to provide education and skill development training so that they can contribute to the national economy. Most of the South Sudanese refugees in Ethiopia are women and children. So delivery of essential services is required there along with proper care arrangement, psychological care of the child in friendly spaces (Meyer et al., 2019).

5.3 Kenya

Almost 114,432 South Sudanese Refugees are hosted in Kaakuma camps and Kolabeyei settlements in Kenya (Martin, 2016). The need of emergency humanitarian aids for ensuring food, hygiene, transitional shelters are highly required in this area. Though significant improvement had been adopted in integrating them into national services. Additional efforts are recommended for sustainable capacity in the hosting areas for future peaceful co-existence (Meyer et al., 2019).

5.4 Sudan

Sudan hosting 854,000 individuals of South Sudan (Martin, 2016). Public unawareness and birth registration are creating vulnerability. Lack of adequate access in the labor market and overpopulation pressure are increasing their assistance need day by day. Health and nutrition are the big threats in Sudan (Auntu et al., 2021). Shortage of adequate water and latrines, dependency on wood for cooking, housing, and lighting where only 5% refugee can buy woods by selling their rations (Martin, 2016). Most of the refugees are residing in remote and underdeveloped areas in Sudan where high levels of poverty exist with poor infrastructures, limited health care services, water supply, poor education system, and so on. They are identified as a risk for host community livelihood opportunities and environmental degradation.

5.5 Uganda

Uganda is introduced as the third-largest refugee-hosting country in the world where almost 1.11 million South Sudanese refugees are taking shelter (Adaku et al., 2016). There are some problems in Uganda as well (Schomerus and Titeca, 2012). There are low educational facilities and sustainable energy production for cooking, housing, and lighting. The living conditions of Uganda for the South Sudanese refugees remain below the international poverty line of US\$1.9 per day (Schomerus and Titeca, 2012). Uganda is a country of low production and productivity with post-harvest losses. Moreover, limited business support loans, microcredit, and low opportunities for skill development training are acting here as a key barrier to earning outside of agriculture (Leonardi, 2013). Limited access to soaps and hygiene supplies enhancing the spread of different disease in refugee areas and host country both. Local integration seems to a great challenge according to the above-mentioned discussion (Leonardi, 2013). As the pressure of hosting the refugee falls mostly over the neighboring country and it is their

moral values and responsibility to keep the borders open for the refugee. Under no situation, they cannot be sent back to their countries till there is a probability of persecution due to their moral obligation (Jacobsen, 2002). In response to this situation, resettlement can be adopted. Almost 28 countries have shown their interest in resettlement. Resettlement has been occurred based on the willingness of the host country under the legal guardianship of UNHCR (Meyer et al., 2019).

The main participants of this resettlement program are Canada, Australia, the USA, New Zealand, Denmark, Sweden, and so on. For example, two million refugees are settled in Thailand from Vietnam (Auntu et al., 2020). In this way, through resettlement, South Sudanese Refugee Crisis in the host country can be resolved (Campbell, 2006). Current host countries can be reluctant from their burden as well as the refugee will receive a comprehensive living standard, so that they can contribute to the economy of the host country. As a result, in the future, they will not be considered burdens (Campbell, 2006).

6. Conclusion

Mitigating the conflict is the first and foremost priority to reduce the pressure on neighboring states. No one can deny economic development is the key component of any nations which facilitating the development of life of a nation. When a nation is not economically solvent that led economic grievances among civilization which facilitated civil war. So many international organizations, World leaders should work for development of the people of Sudan so that people are not engaged with bloody conflict. This things also help to reduce pressure over neighboring countries. Another important things is that South Sudan is considered as one of the second corrupt country , corruption led political instability that driven civil conflict.

But civil conflict led Refugee crisis which is an ongoing crisis that impact on neighboring states of Sudan. The world leaders should ensure financial assistance to the host countries. The host countries must need to introduce the refuge about their culture ,tradition, norms so that they will mixed with them and live peacefully. There are must need to engaged many scholars so that they help to develop new ideas. The present conditions of South Sudan require a rapid and immediate response. Leaders of South Sudan, President Salva Kiir, and Vice President Riek Macher should leave the politics of ethnic confrontation. They should take immediate action on de-escalating the hostilities and should participate in the implementation of the agreement of the resolution of the conflict (ARCSS) that has been signed by both parties. The governing bodies should control their military forces and respect their cease-fire which they had discreetly. The EU had participated with the UN in the United Nations Mission in South Sudan (UNMISS) with their support. They are welcomed in the discussions of the security council of the United Nations. They suggested to provide proper humanitarian assistance and recommended to impose an immediate arms embargo on South Sudan and sanction over the leaders and commanders undermining implementations of the peace agreement(Auntu et al., 2020). The EU recommended all the neighboring countries for keeping the border open and receiving the South Sudanese refugee whom all have fled from their countries for the fear of persecution and for the government of South Sudan to respect the free movement of the people. Finally it can be said that durable solution must need to solve the crisis(Auntu et al., 2020).

7. Recommendations

Some policies are recommended for the resettlement of the South Sudanese refugees. The host country government should uphold the quality of the environment of their refugee camps along with ensuring legal rights and physical protection in the region. It will make them interested in locally integrated after the resettlement in the host countries (Adaku et al., 2016). Birth registration, legal documentation, and data management in collaboration should be preserved for future durable solutions. Promotion of the social cohesion between the refugee and locals should be maintained for the future survival of the South Sudanese refugees in the host countries. The UN, EU, or other international organizations should monitor the refugee after resettlement and assist their necessity. The internal problems of South Sudan should be recognized through a proper equitable and acceptable solutions with the intervention of the international organizations (Auntu et al., 2021).

References

- Auntu, S.K. and Promee, A.T. (2020). Repatriation as a Solution of Afghan Refugee Crisis: A Critical Overview. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 5(6).
- Knopf, A. (2016). Ending South Sudan's Civil War. Council Special Report No. 77, Council on Foreign Relations. Available: https://www.cfr.org/sites/default/files/pdf/2016/11/CSR77_Knopf_South%20Sudan.pdf [January 13, 2020]
- Dryden-Peterson, S. and Hovil, L. (2004). A remaining hope for durable solutions: Local integration of refugees and their hosts in the case of Uganda. *Refugee: Canada's Journal on Refugees*, pp.26-38.
- Campbell, E.H. (2006). Urban refugees in Nairobi: Problems of protection, mechanisms of survival, and possibilities for integration. *Journal of refugee studies*, 19(3), 396-413.
- Jacobsen, K. (2002). Can refugees benefit the state? Refugee resources and African statebuilding. *Journal of Modern African Studies*, pp.577-596.
- Adaku, A., Okello, J., Lowry, B., Kane, J.C., Alderman, S., Musisi, S. and Tol, W.A. (2016). Mental health and psychosocial support for South Sudanese refugees in northern Uganda: a needs and resource assessment. *Conflict and Health*, 10(1), 1-10.
- Saksena, J. and McMorrow, S.L. (2019). Through their eyes: A photovoice and interview exploration of integration experiences of Congolese refugee women in Indianapolis. *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, pp.1-21.
- Schomerus, M. and Titeca, K. (2012). Deals and dealings: inconclusive peace and treacherous trade along the South Sudan-Uganda border. *Africa Spectrum*, 47(2-3), 5-31.
- Leonardi, C. (2013). South Sudanese Arabic and the Negotiation of the Local State, c. 1840—2011. *The Journal of African History*, 351-372.
- Blanchard, L. P. (2014). The Crisis in South Sudan. Congressional Research Service.
- Kline, S. (2003). Push and pull factors in international nurse migration. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, 35(2), 107-111
- Hovil, Lucy and Zachary A. L. (2015). Forced displacement and the crisis of citizenship in Africa's Great Lakes Region: Rethinking refugee protection and durable solutions. *Refugee: Canada's Journal on Refugees*, 31(2), 39-50.
- Kaiser, T. (2010). Dispersal, division and diversification: durable solutions in South Sudanese Refugees. *Journal of Eastern African Studies*, 4(1), 44-60.

- Vasquez, J.A. (1998). *The power of power politics: From classical realism to neotraditionalism* (No. 63). Cambridge University Press.
- Meyer, S.R., Meyer, E., Bangirana, C., Mangan, P.O. and Stark, L. (2019). Protection and well-being of adolescent refugees in the context of a humanitarian crisis: Perceptions from South Sudanese refugees in Uganda. *Social Science & Medicine*, 221, 79-86.
- Martin, S.F. (2016). The global refugee crisis. *Georgetown Journal of International Affairs*, pp.5-11.
- Hansen, R. (2018). The comprehensive refugee response framework: A commentary. *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 31(2), 131-151.
- Labiso, T. T. (2020). Challenges and Boons of Refugee on the Host Communities: In the Case of Benishangul-Gumuz Regional state, Western Ethiopia. *Environmental Science and natural resources*.
- Mustafa, I. & Mohamed, K. (2020). protecting south sudanese refugees covid 19. Available: <https://www.unicef.org/sudan/stories/protecting-south-sudanese-refugees-covid-19>[March 30, 2021].
- Auntu, S. K., Faria, N. & Siddika, S. (2021). Local Integration of the South Sudanese Refugee: Exploring Impact on the Neighboring States. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 5(1). Available: <http://ijsab.com/wp-content/uploads/5084.pdf> [March 28, 2021]

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